

Guidelines and Style for IRRI Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

New upland rice varieties for Senegal

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DJ.11.509 and IRAT133 are upland rices that have been tested for 4 yr by the National Rice Improvement Program in collaboration with the West Africa Rice Development Association at the ISRA Sefa Station. Results of direct-seeded varietal trials comparing the two rices with local 144 B/9 are in the table.

The new upland varieties have short duration (90–100 d) and are adapted to the local short rainy season (see table). They require specific crop management

because their vegetative period is short and tillering time is very limited. The new varieties performed well except in 1980 and 1982 when the local variety outyielded them.

The varieties were selected from TUNSART/TN1/H4 crossed in Senegal, and IRAT10 crossed at the Institut de Recherches Agronomiques Tropicales, Bouaké, Ivory Coast. DJ.11.509 is a semidwarf photoperiod-insensitive line and has highly synchronized flowering. It has longer grains than IRAT10. IRAT133 has intermediate plant height and photoperiod insensitivity. It has excellent early seedling vigor and intermediate tillering capacity. *ℒ*

Results of variety test of IRAT133 and DJ.11.509 in Senegal.^a

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	1979 (911.9 mm)	1980 (699.3 mm)	1981 (1021.6 mm)	1982 (794.4 mm)
IRAT133	3.0	2.0	3.8	2.8
DJ.11.509	4.8	2.9	2.9	2.2
144 B/9	3.0	2.2	2.2	2.4

^a Values in parentheses indicate rainfall.

Land races of aromatic rice discovered in Taiwan

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Until recently, aromatic rice was not extensively grown in Taiwan, although rice has been grown there for thousands of years. Breeding for scented rice began at Chiayi Agricultural Experiment Station in 1977. Several promising aromatic strains, both sinica (keng) and indicas, were developed. Among them, Chianung-yu 269 (source of aroma: Taishosen from Japan), a sinica type, and Chianung-sen-yu 43 (source of aroma: IR841 from IRRI), an indica, are

expected to be named as varieties in 1985.

In 1983, we discovered at Hualien District Agricultural Improvement Station that traditional aromatic rices were widely grown, though on limited hectareage, in many parts of the district. Farmers who planted the aromatic rice belong to the Ai-mei aboriginal tribe, one of several tribes in Taiwan. Other tribes do not plant aromatic rices.

The aromatic rices grown by Ai-mei farmers are tall and leafy with large panicles and long-awned grains. Yields are low (see table). Although the exact number of land races in the area has not been determined, there are large intra- and inter-varietal differences; therefore